

Final PhD Thesis Report

KENTUCKY

**Exploring the evolutionary
success of the antibiotic
resistant Salmonella
Kentucky ST198.**

Responsible Partner: Sciensano

Contributing partners: INRAE

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1. PhD Project team composition

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2. Abstract

Mobile genetic elements MGEs facilitate the evolution of multiple drug-resistant Enterobacteriaceae like *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Salmonella enterica*, and *Escherichia coli* through molecularly intricate mechanisms such as conjugation, transduction, and transposition. Plasmids, via conjugation, can allow cell-to-cell transfer of antibiotic resistance genes while transposable elements can convert plasmid-borne resistance genes to chromosomally encoded resistance and vice versa. Thus adding an important dimension to the spread and acquisition of multiple drug resistance by fixing the horizontally acquired resistance into vertically inherited one. Yet, the potential negative effects of acquiring mobile genetic elements and resistance genes on the fitness of recipient cells are poorly understood. Plasmids might provide an advantage to their host in specific niches, yet plasmid acquisition is an evolutionary expensive process rendering plasmid persistence within a bacterial population, paradoxical. Consequently, bacterial cells have evolved sophisticated regulation mechanisms to modulate the expression of horizontally acquired genes. In Enterobacteriaceae, the H-NS protein can selectively insulate and silence xenogeneic horizontally acquired genes to mitigate the cost of plasmid acquisition.

In this project, various genetic engineering techniques were instigated to increase the conjugation and transposition efficiency in order to maximize the likelihood of visualizing the transfer dynamics of the IncHI-archetype plasmid pR27 and the carried ISEcp1 in real time using microfluidics and fluorescence microscopy. Furthermore, the dynamics of H-NS, a silencer of horizontally acquired genes, were investigated in real-time upon plasmid acquisition. pR27 also carries its own copy of H-NS, which likely reduces its acquisition cost. Our results showed conservation of the DNA-binding domain among plasmid-derived (i.e., R27) and chromosomally encoded H-NS. Moreover, the plasmid-borne H-NS copy (i.e., R27) could partially complement a chromosomal H-NS deficiency in a gene-dependent manner. Finally, using live microscopy we have timed and quantified the expression of plasmid-derived H-NS at the very moment of plasmid acquisition.

3. Introduction and Objectives

Salmonella enterica serovar Kentucky (*S. Kentucky*) is a common causative agent of gastroenteritis in humans. It is one of the most notorious *Salmonella* serotypes, as it is strongly associated with antimicrobial resistance (AMR). Ciprofloxacin-resistant *S. Kentucky* can gain additional antibiotic resistance determinants through the acquisition of locally circulating plasmid-borne ESBL, AmpC, and/or carbapenemase genes. Most recently, the situation has worsened, as ECDC launched an Urgent Inquiry (UI-464) on a CIP^R *S. Kentucky* ST198 strain carrying a chromosomally integrated *bla*_{CTX-M-14b} gene encoding for cephalosporin resistance. The insertion event was traced back to Malta, but the strain has already spread to Belgium, the UK, and five other EU countries. In this Ph.D. project, we will investigate (i) what explains the evolutionary success of the multidrug-resistant *S. Kentucky* ST198 clone, and (ii) what is the mechanisms of the integration (and potential further transfer) of the ESBL gene in its chromosome. As of 2022, 654 IncHI uniquely typed plasmids are found around the world. Most of these plasmids are found in *S. enterica*, *E. coli*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Moreover, IncHI plasmids are important spreaders of antibiotic resistance genes, ca. 40% of colistin resistance-carrying plasmids in Europe, belong to the IncHI group. Due to its clinical significance, the *S. Kentucky* resident-IncHI- mega-plasmid carrying the ISECP1-*bla*_{CTX-M-14B} transposition unit was chosen as a focal point for our fluorescent tagging strategy. Yet, wet-lab experiments backed with *in silico* analysis indicated that the plasmid is non-conjugable, most probably due to truncation in the transfer region. Thus, we reasoned to shift to the prototype IncHI1 plasmid (R27), a self-transmissible plasmid with fully characterized conjugation machinery (Craig et al., 2000) that is capable of transfer between members of the *Enterobacteriaceae*.

The transposition mechanism of ISECP1 is obscure so we decided to develop fluorescent reporters based on the partitioning system *parS*/*ParB* to differentially label the pR27 backbone and the ISEcp1-*bla*_{CTX-M-14b} unit. *parS* is a cis-acting centromere-like sequence to which a partitioning protein *ParB* selectively binds. Two alternative partitioning systems were instigated namely, P1 Phage-derived and *Lactococcus lactis*-derived *parS*/*ParB*. The latter system has minimal interference with DNA replication. Yet, the system is derived from gram-positive bacteria and needs to be optimized to a gram-negative host. First, we labeled the pR27 backbone with a P1-*parS* sequence. Next, we tagged ISECP1-*bla*_{CTX-M-14B} transposition with *lactis-parS* sequence *in vitro*, followed by cloning the assembled unit into pR27. Then we codon-optimized *lactis-parB* protein according to *Salmonella* codon usage and fused the optimized-*parB* to *msf*-GFP under an IPTG inducible promoter. We tagged optimized *parB* at the N-terminus and C-terminus with both flexible and rigid linkers. Yet we failed to obtain localized foci *in vivo*.

We decided to move to alternative fluorescent reports based on P1/ pMT partitioning system (Nielsen et al., 2006). In parallel, the *in vitro*- mating assays of pR27 indicated a conjugation efficiency of 10⁻⁵-10⁻⁶ at 25C which is challenging to study under the fluorescent microscope. Hence, several genetic approaches were instigated to increase the conjugation efficiency to be able to track the transfer event in real time. first, we replaced the conjugation repressor *htdA* with pMT *parS* sequence to obtain a 2-3 log increase in the conjugation efficiency (Whelan et al., 1994). Next, we tried overexpressing *trhR* and *trhY* genes in trans to further increase the conjugation efficiency, since *TrhR* and *TrhY* are involved in the activation of the expression of the four *Tra* operons of pR27. Finally, we opted for knocking out the nucleoid-associated proteins H-NS which is known to repress the conjugation of pR27. The aforementioned approaches resulted in a 4-log increase of the conjugation efficiency of pR27 at 25C

(ca. 1 in 10). Next, we in vitro-labeled the ISECP1-blaCTX-M-14B transposition unit with P1-parS sequence and cloned it into pR27, yielding the reporter double parS labeled plasmid (R27 [Δ htdA::frt-Cm-frt- pMTparS -ISEcp1-P1parS-blaCTX-M-14b]) which conjugate at a frequency of 1 in 10 at 25C. To visualize the transfer of pR27 in real-time we constructed a recipient strain (MA8058 Δ pSLT Δ ara::tetR-Km-CFP:P1parB-YGFP:pMTparB), which encodes orthogonal ParB proteins (Nielsen et al., 2006) fused to fluorescent reporters. Via a microfluidic platform we were able to track in real-time the transfer of double parS labeled plasmid (R27 [Δ htdA::frt-Cm-frt- pMTparS -ISEcp1-P1parS-blaCTX-M-14b) from a donor *S. enterica* cell (MA8058 Δ pSLT; Δ hns) to a recipient cell (MA8058 Δ pSLT Δ ara::tetR-Km-CFP:P1parB-YGFP:pMTparB).

Since plasmid conjugation also comes with significant fitness costs to the host, a silencer of horizontally acquired genes is studied (i.e. H-NS). H-NS is known to bind high AT-rich DNA loci. Horizontally acquired DNA is likely to have a high percentage of AT content compared to the resident chromosome. The host H-NS is believed to transcriptionally insulate xenogenic (horizontally acquired) DNA and thereby play a major role (barrier) during conjugative plasmid transfer. *In vivo* H-NS dynamics during plasmid acquisition are thus of interest to track in real-time with fluorescence microscopy. First, we made a host H-NS deletion, to study the effect of losing this master regulator. Next, the host H-NS was translationally fused to a fast-maturing fluorescent reporter (SYFP2) to study the effect of H-NS on horizontally acquired genes. Surprisingly, pR27 also carries an H-NS homolog and the function of plasmid-derived H-NS is obscure. we are also motivated to test the interchangeability of plasmid-borne H-NS and host-borne H-NS copies. Hence, we constructed a C-terminal fusion of R27-derived H-NS with a fluorescent reporter (mScarlet-I). The *In vivo* dynamics of plasmid-borne H-NS and host-borne H-NS copies will be studied in real time at the very first moment of plasmid acquisition. besides, we are trying to overexpress ISEcp1 to obtain log(s) increase in the transposition frequency and consequently, we could visualize the transposition of blaCTX-M-14b and the carries IS element from the plasmid to the chromosome.

4. Methodology, Scientific Result, and Discussion

Full-length sequencing of *S. Kentucky* isolates

Short read sequencing libraries of isolates were prepared with an Illumina Nextera XT DNA Library Preparation Kit and sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq instrument with a 250-bp paired-end protocol (MiSeq v3 chemistry) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Trimming of the short reads was performed with Trimmomatic (version 0.32). First the Illuminaclip option was used to remove the Nextera adapter sequences. Then a sliding window approach of four bases and trimming when the Phred score dropped below 30 was employed. Lastly, the leading and trailing bases of a read were removed when the Phred score dropped below 3. Lastly, all reads that were smaller than 50 bp were removed.

The MinION long read sequencing library was prepared by using the 1D ligation sequencing kit (SQK-LSK108, Oxford Nanopore) according to the manufacturer's protocol for genomic DNA without barcoding. In total there were two MinION flowcells used, and libraries with 8 and 12 barcodes were loaded on them respectively (EXP-NBD103, Oxford Nanopore). For the Flongle long read sequencing

libraries, the adapted 1D ligation protocol for Flongles was used with the SQK-LSK109 sequencing kit. From each isolate 500 ng of DNA was used at the start of the protocol. DNA repair was no longer optional in SQK-LSK109 and therefore this was performed for the Flongle runs. In the SQK-LSK109 there are two washing buffers the SFB and LFB of which the latter enriches for DNA fragments >3,000 bp. Both these washing buffers and the inclusion or exclusion of the shearing step were used on separate Flongle flowcells. Moreover, on the Flongles no barcoding was performed. Basecalling and demultiplexing of the Nanopore sequences was performed with Guppy (3.2.4). Then all Nanopore reads with a quality score lower than 7 or a length lower than 1000 were removed with NanoFilter. For

Figure 1. Belgian *S. Kentucky* strains in their international context.

Moreover, the latter isolate also contained the ESBL gene *bla*_{CMY-2} on a plasmid. Isolate S18BD05011 contained no ESBL genes on its chromosome, but *bla*_{CTX-M-104} and *bla*_{TEM-1B} were localised on two different plasmids, contigs 2 and 3, respectively. Initially, ResFinder assigned *bla*_{CTX-M-14b} to isolate S18BD05011 with an identity of 99.89%, but with the CARD database² it was determined that a point mutation at position 824 corresponds to the *bla*_{CTX-M-104} gene. Upon further inspection, a **region of 2850 bp including the ESBL gene was found to be similar in the chromosome of S16BD08730 and S18BD03394 and in the plasmid (contig 2) of S18BD05011.** In these regions, there was only a 1 bp difference, resulting in either the *bla*_{CTX-M-14b} (S16BD08730 and S18BD03394 on the chromosome) or *bla*_{CTX-M-104} (S18BD05011, on a plasmid) variants. The ISEcp1B transposase, which is part of the IS1380 family, was detected in this region adjacent to the ESBL gene (Figure 2). In the NCBI database there

the output of the sequencing runs and the theoretical coverage of each sample see table S14. The statistics of the Illumina reads was determined with FastQC and of the Nanopore reads was determined with NanoStat. Raw sequencing data and the de novo assemblies were submitted to NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) and NCBI Genbank.

The chromosomes of isolates S16BD08730, S18BD03394 and S18BD05011 share the AMR genes *aac(3)-I_d*, *aph(3'')-I_b*, *aph(3')-I_a*, *aph(6)-I_d*, *sul1*, *tet(A)* and *aac(6')-I_{aa}*. All these AMR genes except for *aac(6')-I_{aa}* were localised very close to each other and by aligning this region to the NCBI nucleotide database it was determined that these genes were part of a *Salmonella* genetic island 1 K (SGI1-K). Two isolates (S16BD08730 and S18BD03394) carried the ESBL gene *bla*_{CTX-M-14b} in the chromosome, while one isolate (S18BD00684) contained another ESBL gene, *bla*_{TEM-1B}, in the chromosome.

were no exact matches, but with a literature search, a description of this 2850 bp fragment was found in Lei et al. 2020 in the chromosome of a *S. Kentucky* isolated from Chinese poultry.

Figure 2. Genome rearrangements of the ISECP – bla_{CTX-M-14} cluster.

Abundance of insertion sequences and AMR genes

A dataset of *Klebsiella Pneumoniae* assemblies at the contig level has been downloaded from the public database 'NCBI Assemblies'. To investigate the presence of associations between IS elements and AMR genes in the dataset, detection of antimicrobial resistance has been carried out through ResFinder, detection of IS elements through ISEScan, detection of replicons through PlasmidFinder and prediction of the origin for each contig with the machine learning program RFPlasmid. By comparing the coordinates on the contigs of the detected elements, distances between IS and AMR genes have been calculated as the number of bp between the end of one element and the start of the other, and stored in python data frames.. This process has been done by measuring the number of associations that would be present in the dataset for each of the most common IS

families when considering different thresholds. The value chosen was 10,000 bp, as it would allow to capture a good number of IS6 associations without overestimating the number of associations for any of the other relevant IS families.

The number of associations in the dataset was thus approximately 30,000 on 4,325 samples, the large majority of which were located on a contig that was predicted to be plasmid-derived. The IS family that presented the highest number of associations with different AMR types was IS6, which was particularly associated with aminoglycosides and beta-lactams, followed by IS91, IS1380 and IS5.

Considering specifically beta-lactamases, the IS family that is most often associated with genes of this class of resistance was IS1182, followed by IS21, IS1380 and IS6. In particular, the genes blaCTX-M-15, blaCTX-M-3, blaKPC.3 seem to be often found close to many of the IS families present in the dataset.

The IS1380 family can be found close to the following beta-lactam resistance genes, blaCTX-M-15, blaCTX-M-132, blaCTX-M-3, blaCTX-M-36, and blaKPC-2. Among these, the CTX-M-15 gene is by far the most relevant in terms of number of associations, most of which are found on plasmid-derived contigs.

The ISEcp1 element belongs to the IS1380 family of insertion sequence and indeed is one of the most important elements that mobilise blaCTX-M-15 genes (Hamamoto et al., 2020). In this context, ISEcp1 is included between a IRL and a IRR sequence and is found upstream of the blaCTX-M-15 gene. It can mobilise its downstream region with variable lengths, creating a transposition unit through the recognition of the IRL and the IRR, or an alternative IRR (IRRalt) (Hamamoto et al., 2020). This transposition is called a one-ended transposition (Poirel, Decousser and Nordmann, 2005). Interestingly, ISEcp1 is known to also provide a promoter sequence to different AMR genes in its right side (Poirel, Decousser and Nordmann, 2003).

Insertion of P1-parS and lactis-parS labeled transposition unit into pR27

pKD46, a plasmid with temperature-sensitive replicon, encoding lambda Red recombinases was electroporated into MA8508ΔpSLT strain. Next, pR27 was conjugated by filter mating to MA8508ΔpSLT containing pKD46. In short, cultures of the donor (E.coli, pR27) and recipient strains (MA8508ΔpSLT containing pKD46) were grown in LB supplemented with the required antibiotics at 25°C in static conditions for 16 h. Cells were washed with 0.1M MgSO₄ to eliminate the antibiotics. The recipient strain suspension (0.4 ml) and donor strain suspension (0.1 ml) were mixed on a 0.22 μm

membrane and incubated at 25°C for 2 h. Serial dilutions were plated in appropriate media to select for trans-conjugants (MA8508ΔpSLT containing pKD46 and pR27).

P1-parS was then PCR amplified as P1-parS- frt-cat-frt fragment and electroporated into MA8508ΔpSLT containing pKD46 and pR27 to be inserted in an intergenic region on pR27 backbone via lambda red recombineering (Datsenko et al; 2000). Next, we flipped the chloramphenicol cassette using pCP20, a plasmid encoding Flp recombinase. To label the ISEcp1-bla_{CTX-M-14b} unit with *Lactococcus lactis*-derived parS, we PCR amplified the unit as two fragments with the 18bp parS sequence as an overhang (GGGGCTAAATTTAGCCCC). The two fragments were then assembled in vitro by gibsson assembly and inserted into pR27 backbone by homologous recombination (Datsenko et al; 2000). The 18bp parS sequence was inserted downstream the terminator region of the ISEcp1 gene and upstream the promoter region of bla_{CTX-M-14b} gene. We then confirmed the insertion of P1 and *Lactococcus lactis*-derived parS together with the conservation of the ISEcp1, bla_{CTX-M-14b} genes by sequencing.

Optimizing P1-ParB and Lactis-ParB Proteins

First, we separately inserted by recombineering the two parS sequences into the chromosomes of MA8508ΔpSLT to serve as a positive control for fluorescent microscopy. Next, we transformed the MA8508ΔpSLT labeled with P1-parS and lactis-parS with pALA2705 and pMK17-01 respectively. pALA2705 plasmid encodes P1-parB N-terminally fused to mCherry whereas pMK17-01 encodes lactis-parB C-terminally fused to msfGFP. Time-lapse microscopy experiments showed only localized foci with P1-parB-mCherry, indicating that lactis-parB failed to bind its cognate parS sequence. Thus we reasoned to codon optimize the lactis-parB protein to a gram-negative host using the genescript™ platform. Then the codon-optimized lactis-parB protein was then cloned into a variant of pALA2705 encoding GFP to obtain pALA2706 (lactis-parB N-terminally fused to GFP). pALA2706 was then transformed into MA8508ΔpSLT labeled with lactis-parS. The microscopy experiment showed again diffused fluorescence. We thought to change the fusion type into C- terminal fusion and try different linkers. In short, pALA2706 was PCR linearized to remove GFP- lactis-ParB. Then msfGFP and lactis-ParB were PCR amplified, assembled in vitro to produce lactis-parB C-terminally fused to msfGFP with two different linkers (SSSRGSGGEAAKAGS, (SGGGG)₄), and ligated back to PCR-linearized pALA2706 by Gibson assembly. The two variants of the plasmid were then separately transformed to MA8508ΔpSLT labeled with lactis-parS. yet we failed to obtain localized foci. The inability of *lactis*-ParB to bind its cognate parS sequence in vivo may be attributed to improper folding in gram-negative host despite being codon-optimized. It is also possible that parB fails to oligomerize upon binding so we don't observe the localized focus over the background diffused fluorescence. Moreover, in *E.coli*, the integration host factors (IHF) bind specific sequences on P1-parS and facilitate the binding of P1-parB to P1-parS (Barbara Funnel., 1991) and since lactis-parS does not carry an IHF-binding sequence it might have failed to attract the partitioning machinery.

Construction of a reporter plasmid based on P1, pMT parS/ ParB partition system

pR27 displays a conjugation efficiency of ca. 10⁻⁵ at 25°C and ca. 10⁻⁷ at 37°C. Since conjugation of the wild-type R27 plasmid is only a one in a 10⁻⁵ event, three genetic engineering approaches were

instigated to increase the conjugation efficiency of pR27 to maximize the likelihood of observing the conjugation in Real-time. **(i)** The first approach was knocking out the conjugation repressor HtdA which is involved in the repression of four tra operons and has a pivotal role in the growth phase dependency of R27 conjugation. In short, pMT parS was PCR amplified as pMT-parS- frt-cat-frt fragment, and the fragment was electroporated into MA8508ΔpSLT containing pKD46 and pR27 to replace *htdA* gene. In vitro conjugation assay has shown a 2-3 log increase in the conjugation efficiency of pR27, *htdA* mutant as compared to the wild-type. We then labeled the transposition unit with P1-parS as previously described followed by electroporation into MA8508ΔpSLT containing pKD46 and pR27(pMT-labelled, Δ*htdA*), yielding double parS labelled pR27 (R27 [Δ*htdA*::frt-Cm-frt- pMTparS -ISEcp1-P1parS-blaCTX-M-14b]). **(ii)** Next, we opted for overexpressing the conjugation regulators TrhR and TrhY which are known to activate the expression of four different Tra operons (Gibert et al; 2016). The *trhR* and *trhY* genes were PCR amplified and assembled in vitro (i.e. Gibson assembly) under a strong constitutive promoter (J23119). The assembled construct was electroporated (MA8058 pKD46 ΔpSLT), to be inserted into an intergenic region, flanked by two terminators to prevent read-through. The transformants were PCR confirmed, however, the sequencing data showed multiple mutations resulting in an early stop codon in *trhY*. In a second attempt, we tried to over-express *trhR* and *trhY* in cis on pR27 (R27 [Δ*htdA*::frt-Cm-frt-pMTparS]). The native promoter of *trhR* and *trhY* was replaced by the strong constitutive promoter (J23119). After the exchange of the native promoter, the construct was PCR confirmed, however, frameshift mutations were found in the *trhR* rendering the construct not functional. Previous work by Forns et al. (2005), and Gibert et al. (2014) suggests that conjugation of R27 can be increased by either knocking out the *hns* gene of the chromosome of the donor cells or the plasmid itself. **(iii)** The third approach to increase the conjugation efficiency was thus based on the deletion of *hns* in the chromosome of the donor strain (MA8058 pKD46 ΔpSLT). In short, The ORF of *hns* was replaced by frt-Km-frt except for the first 11 amino acids (MA8058 pKD46 ΔpSLT Δ*hns*::frt-Km-frt). Next, The double parS labelled plasmid (R27 [Δ*htdA*::frt-Cm-frt- pMTparS -ISEcp1-P1parS-blaCTX-M-14b]) was conjugated from a Δ*hns* strain *S. enterica* strain (MA8058 ΔpSLT). The respective conjugation frequencies were calculated as the transconjugant over recipient ratio (T/R) and the transconjugant over donor ratio (R/D). At 25°C the T/R conjugation efficiency is ca. 1.12×10^{-1} and the T/D conjugation efficiency is ca. 7.70×10^{-2} . Hence, Conjugation efficiency has increased from ca. 10^{-5} (pR27 wild type) to ca. one in 10 by knocking out both HtdA and H-NS.

Construction of the fluorescent recipient strain to visualize the transfer of pR27 in real-time.

Next, a recipient strain, which encodes orthogonal ParB proteins (Nielsen et al., 2006) fused to fluorescent reporters (MA8058 ΔpSLT Δ*ara*::tetR-Km-CFP:P1parB-YGFP:pMTparB), was assembled, to visualize the double parS tagged R27 plasmid. These proteins are under the control of an inducible, non-leaky promoter PLtetO-1 which is repressed by TetR. The system can be induced with 200 ng/mL anhydrotetracycline (ATC). We reasoned to assemble cognate parB proteins fused to fluorescent markers into a chromosomal operon under the control of an inducible promoter to avoid ectopic expression from the plasmid. The strain was constructed through 3 consecutive steps. First, the arabinose operon was deleted from MA8058 ΔpSLT strain and replaced by tetA-sacB cassette by positive selection on tetA. Second, the cognate parB proteins translationally fused to fluorescent reporters (CFP:P1parB-YGFP:pMTparB) were PCR amplified and electroporated into MA8058 ΔpSLT, pKD46, Δ*ara*::tetA-sacB to replace tetA-sacB under the native arabinose promoter by negative selection

against sacB/tetA. (Li et al., 2013). Finally, the native arabinose promoter was crossed out and replaced by an inducible, molecularly evolved PLtetO-1.

Next, To validate both the reporter plasmid and the recipient strain, pR27 plasmid labelled with pMTparS and P1parS (R27 [Δ htdA::f_{rt}-Cm-f_{rt}-pMTparS ISEcp1-P1parS-blaCTX-M-14b]), was conjugated to the recipient strain (MA8058 Δ pSLT Δ ara::tetR-Km-CFP:P1parB-YGFP:pMTparB) and the resulting transconjugants were tracked in real-time with fluorescence microscopy (AB-glycerol at 30°C; ATC at final conc. 200 ng/ml). This results in overlapping foci between the green (YGFP) (the plasmid backbone) and blue (CFP)(the transposon) channel as can be seen in Figure 1. The foci are shown in the mid-cell at 0 min,18 min, and 36 min (after cell division). At 90 minutes two foci are segregated from the mid-cell before cell division (Lawley et al.;2003). Recipient cells that carry WT pR27 showed only diffused fluorescence (data not shown) indicating that the localized green and blue foci are likely due to the pMT-parS (plasmid backbone) and P1-parS (transposon) respectively.

Figure 3. Recipient cell with double parS labeled R27 with YGFP and CFP fluorescent foci. The double parS labelled R27 plasmid (R27 [Δ htdA::f_{rt}-Cm-f_{rt}- pMTparS ISEcp1-P1parS-blaCTX-M-14b]) was conjugated to the recipient strain (MA8058 Δ pSLT Δ ara::tetR-Km-CFP:P1parB-YGFP:pMTparB). The resulting transconjugants were followed with time-lapse fluorescence microscopy on AB-glycerol pads at 30°C. Both the YGFP (plasmid backbone) and CFP (transposon) foci are overlapping at the mid-cell during the time-lapse (0-36 min). The plasmid is segregating from the mid-cell after 90 minutes. Pictures are an overlay of phase contrast, green fluorescence, and blue fluorescence.

Tracking the transfer dynamics of pR27 in real-time via microfluidics

The next step was to track the conjugation of the R27 plasmid using time-lapse fluorescence microscopy. This was performed numerous times but did not yield any conjugation events. Recent research performed by Carranza et al. (2021) also did not observe any conjugation events with time-lapse fluorescence microscopy. They hypothesize that the agar pad might be inhibiting the conjugation. Nolivos et al. (2019) were able to capture conjugation events in real-time only via a microfluidic platform. Hence we reasoned to use a microfluidic platform to track the conjugation in real-time. Donor cells (MA8058 Δ pSLT; Δ hns; pR27 [Δ htdA::f_{rt}-Cm-f_{rt}- pMTparS -ISEcp1-P1parS-blaCTX-M-14b]), were mixed with recipient cells (MA8058 Δ pSLT Δ ara::tetR-Km-CFP:P1parB-YGFP:pMTparB) in 1:4 ratio respectively and loaded into a chamber in a microfluidic chip. Time-lapse fluorescence microscopy was performed at 25C with an inverted Ti-Eclipse, Nikon microscope.

GFP filter (FITC single emission filter and quad-edge dichroic filter-395/470/550/640 nm) and CFP filter (Emission filter Em475/20+triple excitation filter) were used. Snapshots of the cells were made every 15 for a total of 6h. After 90 min foci started to emerge indicating a transfer event.

Figure 4. A 1:4 mixture of the donor (non-fluorescent) and recipient cells (fluorescent) growing at 25C in a microfluidic chamber under an inverted Ti-Eclipse, Nikon microscope. On the Left panel, cells after loading into the chip (t0) show a mixture of non-fluorescent donor cells and recipient cells with diffused fluorescence. The right panel shows some of the recipient cells after 90 min (t90) start showing localized foci, marking independent conjugation events.

In Vivo dynamics of host H-NS: Construction of host- H-NS translational fusions and Δ hns

H-NS was translationally fused to a fast-maturing fluorescent protein, SYFP2, with a maturation time of 4.1 ± 0.3 min (t50) at 37°C. A C-terminal translational fusion was constructed using a flexible linker GSAGSAAGSGEF as previously reported by Gao et al. (2017) (MA8058 pKD46 Δ pSLT hns:SYFP2-frt-Km-frt.). The construct was confirmed by both PCR and sequencing. Since SYFP2 might be blocking the native function of H-NS, a second version of the translational fusion was made. Different fluorescent proteins might have different physical properties in terms of phototoxicity and photostability, that's why a second translational fusion protein was made by fusing H-NS to mCerulean3 as described before (MA8058 pKD46 Δ pSLT hns:mCer3-frt-Cm-frt, The construct was PCR and sequence confirmed.

Figure 5. Time-lapse fluorescence microscopy for hns:SYFP2(left panel) and hns:mcer3 (right panel) HNS- translation fusions showed nucleoid structures as expected since HNS is a master regulator and known to be bound to various loci across the chromosomes of actively dividing cells. Cells were grown on AB-glucose pads at 30°C. Red bars indicate a length of 1 μ m.

Next, *hns* knock-out mutant was made to phenotypically compare the impact of the H-NS translational fusions. The ORF of *hns* was replaced by *frt-Km-frt* except for the first 11 amino acids (MA8058 pKD46 Δ pSLT Δ *hns*::*frt-Km-frt*). Knocking-out *hns* is known to decrease swarming because H-NS is normally regulating gene expression of flagellar genes. Furthermore, the deletion of H-NS is known to cause a growth deficiency in *S. enterica*. The phenotypic comparison was thus based on a growth assay and swarming motility assay. Since fusing H-NS with mCerulean3 or SYFP2 might lead to a knock-down (or even knock-out) of H-NS, the swarming motility of the strains was tested and compared to the wild-type (MA8058 pKD46 Δ pSLT) and a Δ *hns* strain (MA8058 Δ pSLT Δ *hns*::*frt-Km-frt*). The *hns*:SYFP2 shows no significant difference in swarming and growth compared to wild-type.

pR27 partially complements a Δ *hns* swarming and growth phenotype

Forns et al. (2005) showed that pR27 partially complements Δ *hns* phenotypes like growth (at 25°C) and hemolysin production in *E. coli*. To test this complementation in *S. enterica*, the double *parS* labelled pR27 plasmid (R27 [Δ htdA::*frt-Cm-frt*- pMT*parS* ISEcp1-P1*parS*-blaCTX-M-14b]) was conjugated to the Δ *hns* strain (MA8058 pKD46 Δ pSLT Δ *hns*::*frt-Km-frt*). The resulting transconjugant was used for a swarming motility assay and compared to the Δ *hns* and wild-type strain. The transconjugant strain shows a significant difference from both the Δ *hns* strain ($p=1.1 \times 10^{-4}$), and the wild-type strain ($p=0.024$), meaning that a partial recovery to the wild-type phenotype occurred. Next, growth experiment was also performed for (A) wild-type cells (MA8058 pKD46 Δ pSLT), (B) Δ *hns* (MA8058 pKD46 Δ pSLT Δ *hns*::*frt-Km-frt*) and (C) Δ *hns* complemented with double *parS* labelled pR27 (R27 [Δ htdA::*frt-Cm-frt*- pMT*parS* ISEcp1-P1*parS*-blaCTX-M-14b]). As shown in figure 4., almost no cell divisions were observed for the Δ *hns* strain (B). while Δ *hns* cells complemented with the pR27 plasmid (C) were able to partially recover the growth-deficient phenotype.

Figure 6. Comparison of growth of wild-type, Δ *hns* and Δ *hns* complemented with R27. A) WT = MA8058 pKD46 Δ pSLT, B) Δ *hns* = MA8058 pKD46 Δ pSLT Δ *hns*::*frt-Km-frt* and C) Δ *hns* + R27 = MA8058 pKD46 Δ pSLT Δ *hns*::*frt-Km-frt* pR27[Δ htdA::*frt-Cm-frt*- pMT*parS* ISEcp1-P1*parS*-blaCTX-M-14b]. Time points were chosen based on cell divisions of the wild-type cells. Time-lapse fluorescence microscopy was performed with AB-glucose agar pads at 37°C. Δ *hns* does not divide and shows elongated growth. When Δ *hns* is complemented with R27, a partial recovery of growth is observed. Red bars indicate a length of 10 μ m.

To test the interchangeability of plasmid-borne H-NS and host-borne H-NS copies, multiple sequence alignments were performed for distinct groups of H-NS proteins, including native H-NS, StpA, IncHI and IncF plasmid-derived H-NS. Dorman et al. (1999) showed that the H-NS protein family has a conserved DNA-binding domain (TWTXGRXP). Our multiple sequence alignments data suggested the conservation of the 'TWTXGRXP' DNA-binding domain among native H-NS, IncHI, and IncF. The similarities between the DNA-binding domains of native H-NS, and IncHI-derived H-NS might explain the partial complementation of the growth phenotype and the swarming assay of an *hns* knock-out strain since they might be binding to similar DNA sequences. Moreover, Deighan et al. (2003) observed that Sfh (H-NS protein from pSF-R27 from IncHI), and native H-NS can interact with each other. This is supported by Fitzgerald et al. (2020) who observed that the residues for dimerization are conserved between the native H-NS and IncHI-derived H-NS_Yet, The exact function of plasmid-derived HNS is largely obscure thus we opted to C-terminally fuse pR27-H-NS to mScarlet to be able to track in real-time the cross-talk between the host-HNS (*hns*: SYFP2) and the pR27-born H-NS(pR27 *hns*:mScarlet; figure 5). In short, pR27 H-NS was translationally fused to a fast-maturing fluorescent protein, mScarlet-I, with a maturation time of 36 min. The C-terminal translational fusion was constructed using a flexible linker GSAGSAAGSGEF as previously reported by Gao et al. (2017).

Figure 7. Time-lapse fluorescence microscopy for pR27-hns:mScarlet-I. pR27-hns was translationally fused to m-scarlet-I and the plasmid was then conjugated to MA8508 Δ pSLT. Cells were grown on AB-glucose and showed nucleoid structures.

Investigating and visualizing the interplay between R27-H-NS and host H-NS in real-time

We opted to visualize in real-time the conjugation of donor cells carrying pR27-hns:mScarlet-I and recipient cells with fluorescently labeled HNS (*hns*:SYFP2) in order to analyze the timing and level of expression of pR27 H-NS and also to assess the cross-talk between plasmid born and host born H-NS copies. In short Donor cells were mixed with recipient cells in 1:4 ratio respectively and loaded into a chamber in a microfluidic chip. Time-lapse fluorescence microscopy was performed at 25C with an inverted Eclipse Ti2-E microscope (Nikon), using NIS software for image acquisition. Acquisitions were performed using 50% power of a Fluo LED Spectra X light source at 488 and 560 nm excitation wavelengths. Exposure settings were 100 ms for sYFP2 and mScarlet-I and 50 ms for phase contrast. Image acquisition of the cells were made every 5 for a total of 6h. The timelapse primary observations indicated that host and plasmid-born H-NS are overlapping and nucleoid bound and expression of R-27 H-NS in the newly formed transconjugants gradually increased over time and reached donor level

expression after 20 min of plasmid acquisition. Next, we are planning to perform ChIP-seq analysis to probe for host's candidate genes targeted by plasmid-born H-NS.

Figure 8. A 1:4 mixture of the donor (red) and recipient cells (yellow) growing at 25C in a microfluidic chamber under an inverted Ti-Eclipse, Nikon microscope. cells after loading into the chip (t0-t5) show a mixture of red - donor cells and yellow recipient cells with diffused fluorescence. After 15 min of growth, some cells of the yellow population started to turn orange marking the acquisition of the pR27 and the expression of pR27- hns:mScarlet. The expression level in the newly formed trans-conjugants (orange cell) peaked after 20 min of plasmid acquisition to reach the donor-type expression level.

Finally, to track in real-time conjugation dynamics of pR27 and the subsequent transposition of ISECP1-blaCTX-M-14B from the pR27 to the chromosome, we have constructed an over-expression pBAD33 plasmid carrying the transposon (ISEcp1), under strong inducible promoter aiming to increase the transposition frequency. Yet the effect of overexpressing the transposon on the transposition frequency needs to be further evaluated through optical microscopy *in vivo* and GFP hopper assay (Saito et.al., (2010)) *in vitro*. In short, pBAD- ISECP1 overexpression plasmid could theoretically modify the transposition frequency of a promoter-less variant of GFP (regular green fluorescent protein (GFP) which lacks transcriptional and translational start sites) flanked by the canonical inverted repeats (IRR) sequences recognized by the ISEcp1 transposase enzyme. Upon transposition and chromosomal integration, GFP will be expressed and can be detected and sorted by using Fluorescence assisted cell sorting (FACS) and hence we could potentially have a quantitative estimation of the transposition rate *in vitro*.

5. Conclusions and Future work and perspectives

In this Ph.D. project, we have developed fluorescent reporters based on orthogonal parS/ParB systems to differentially label IncHI-archetype plasmid pR27 plasmid and the carried I ISEcp1- blaCTX-M-14b unit. The reporter systems enabled studying the plasmid transfer dynamics at the inter- and intracellular level using time-lapse fluorescent microscopy and microfluidics. We are further optimizing the platform to track intracellular transposition dynamics in real time. Furthermore, the silencer of horizontally acquired genes, H-NS, was investigated together with the interplay between the host-derived and plasmid-born H-NS homologs. Further investigations are required to probe for candidate

genes that are differentially regulated by the homologous H-NS copies and the possible effect of various environmental and/or biochemical cues on the conjugation frequencies.

6. PhD project self-evaluation

As all PhDs pursued during the pandemic, it was an extraordinary time for research. Directly due to consequences of the Covid-19 crisis, the original candidate (Jasper Van der Peet) had to return permanently to The Netherlands in M28. He was replaced by Alaa Albasiony who picked up activities in M34. This caused an inevitable delay in lab progress, and a switch from a more bioinformatic profile to a strong cell biology profile – which is evident from the lab report described in section 2.

The focus through the PhD remained on the transfer dynamics of IncHI type plasmids, abundant in Enterobacterales and very often associated with drug resistance. Through findings in mainly the second year of the project, research focus was lead to H-NS type proteins. These complexes are silencing gene expression in bacterial cells, and we showed their role in conjugation and transfer of mobile genetic elements. As this research particularly required real-time microscopy (which was not defined in such detail in the original project application), .

A second deviation was the inclusion of microfluidics. To confirm our findings and to quantify the observed plasmid transfers, a research visit to the world-renown laboratory of Prof. Christian Lesterlin (CNRS) was performed in Q1 of 2023. This visit allowed to generate conclusive data on the role of plasmid- and chromosomal encoded H-NS proteins, and will undoubtedly lead to high-end publications by the end of the year.

7. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

PhD reference	PhD Project deliverable number	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered (month)	Comments	Integrative categories*
KENTUCKY	D-PhD04-1.1	Genomic Characterization of clinical Salmonella Kentucky strains	M32	M35		3
KENTUCKY	D-PhD04-1.2	Construction of reporter strain, able to show transfer of ESBL gene between plasmid and chromosome	M42	M47		8
KENTUCKY	D-PhD04-1.3	Paper: (Tentative title). Characterization of factors influencing the transfer of ESBL genes from plasmid to chromosome.	M60	M70	Given the results explained in section 2, we aim for publication in Q4 of 2023	8
KENTUCKY	D-PhD04-1.4	Paper 3 (Tentative title). The prevalence of ISeep-1 mediated transfer of ESBL genes to the chromosome among clinically isolated Enterobacteriaceae	M60	M71	Given the results explained in section 2, we aim for publication in Q4 of 2023	8
KENTUCKY	D-PhD04-1.5	Thesis dissertation	M60	M72	The thesis will be defended before the end of 2023	8

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities ; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

PhD reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	Achieved	Comments
KENTUCKY	M-PhD04-1	Quality training completed at Sciensano	M23	M36	Yes	Needed to be repeated for second PhD candidate
KENTUCKY	M-PhD04-2	S. Kentucky strain and genome collection completed	M30	M34	Yes	
KENTUCKY	M-PhD04-3	Completion of hybrid assemblies of four S. Kentucky strain	M36	M38	Yes	
KENTUCKY	M-PhD04-4	Finalization of characterization of MGEs and selection of elements for further study at KULeuven	M46	M50	Yes	
KENTUCKY	M-PhD04-5	Research visit to INRAE	M52	No	Yes	

8. Interactions with JRPs/JIPs or with external (global, EU, national or regional) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), national and international surveillance programmes.

Long-read sequencing was performed according to methodology derived from the Full Force project (JRP-14). Short-term travel grant to CNRS (France) was obtained through MVNA, and performed in Q1 of 2023.

9. Interactions with OHEJP stakeholders

As the reader of this document can undoubtedly identify, the main focus of this research was quite fundamental and mainly focused on academic work to understand the basics of transfer of AMR genes. Therefore, no direct interactions with OHEJP stakeholders were held during this PhD. However, I will formulate a clear recommendation to expand genetic surveillance to the genetic regions flanking AMR genes, to infer their mobility and potential spread within and between bacterial species.

10. Added value and benefits during PhD resulting from being part of the OHEJP doctoral programme and consortium

A great advantage of working in collaboration with public health institutes was the availability of contemporarily collections of Salmonella isolates. As shown above, it was by studying these clinical strains that the transfer of the mobile AMR genes have been identified. Another great advantage was the wide availability and easy access to very specific expertise in the field of plasmid biology. By reaching out and discussing with scientist of the OHEJP network, novel experiments were designed and performed.

11. Transferrable skills and Training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Supervised Master Student thesis (Bioscience Engineering, Gene Technology)	Supervision skills	01/09/2021-30/06/2022	KU Leuven
Technology transfer and exploitation of research.	Research valorization	25/10/2022-10/04/2023	KU Leuven
Supervising Master Student thesis (Bioscience Engineering, Gene Technology)	Supervision skills	01/09/2022- 30/06/2022	KU Leuven
Advanced biological data analysis	Data analysis	29/09/2021- 31/12/2021	KU Leuven
Presentation and seminar skills	Soft skills	01/03/2022- 30/06/2022	KU Leuven

12. Ethical Reviews

Comments of Ethics Advisors, January 2020	Comments PhD Project Supervisor, mid-2020	Comments of Ethics Advisors, October 2020
The beneficiary must confirm that appropriate health and safety procedures conforming to relevant local/national guidelines/legislation are followed for staff involved in this project.	Confirmed	Approved

13. Scientific Publications

No peer-reviewed papers have been published yet, at least four publications are planned for 2023 (see Deliverables chapter). The following poster and oral presentations have been done:

- Albasiony, A., Ceyskens, P.J., Aertsen, A. (2021) Exploring the ISECP-1 mediated chromosomal integration of blaCTX-M-14 in Salmonella Kentucky. Annual Scientific Meeting OHEJP, June 9-11th, 2021. Poster presentation.
- Albasiony, A., Ceyskens, P.J., Aertsen, A. (2022) Exploring the evolutionary success of the antibiotic resistant Salmonella Kentucky ST198. Annual Scientific Meeting OHEJP, April 11-13th, 2022. Poster presentation.
- Albasiony, A., Ceyskens, P.J., Aertsen, A. (2022) Exploring the evolutionary success of the antibiotic resistant Salmonella Kentucky ST198. International Symposium Salmonella and Salmonellosis I3S2022. June 20-22, Saint-Malo, France. Oral presentation.

Zenodo link : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7594718>

14. Additional Outputs

None to report.

15. Specific outcomes to highlight in dissemination and communications

At least four peer-reviewed publication are currently being drafted on this work. Special attention will be given to the transfer of AMR genes between plasmids and chromosomes, and the molecular mechanisms behind.

16. One Health impact

As reflected in section 2, this PhD focused strongly on the molecular mechanisms behind the transfer of antimicrobial resistance genes in and between bacteria. A very large part of the work expanded on the molecular mechanisms behind this transfer, are quite fundamental and cannot be directly translated to policy measures.

However, we observed that a particular mobile genetic element which is highly prevalent in bacteria, ISEcp1, is frequently associated with genes provoking resistance to third-generation cephalosporins. Our data shows that this elements enables the transfer of these AMR genes from plasmids to

chromosomes, leading to fixation of the drug resistance in the genome and vertical heritage of resistance.

Although the net result stays the same (i.e., a drug resistant strain), the public health impact of plasmid-vs chromosomal carriage of drug resistance is different. Once transferred to the chromosome, resistance is stable and can for example no more be reduced by reducing selective pressure. Therefore, results from this thesis strongly argue for expanding surveillance to the genetic regions flanking AMR genes, to infer their mobility and potential spread within and between bacterial species.

17. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	<i>One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022</i>		
Date:	<i>2022-04-11 to 2022-04-13</i>		
Place:	<i>Hybrid</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	Yes
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	No
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity, in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	530	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>	10	<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>	10		

Name of the activity:	<i>International Symposium Salmonella and Salmonellosis I3S2022</i>		
Date:	<i>2022-06-20 to 2022-06-22</i>		
Place:	<i>Saint-Malo, France</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	Yes
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	No
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No

<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	300	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>	25	<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>	5		

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021		
Date:	2021-06-09 00:00:00 to 2021-06-11		
Place:	Online and Copenhagen		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	YES
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	530	Media	

Industry	10	Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers	10		